

Studies on *n*-InP/Redox Electrolyte Photoelectrochemical Cells

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n-InP/NaOH-[Fe(CN)₆]^{4-/3-}/Pt photoelectrochemical cells have been designed and fabricated. The spectral response of the cells revealed a maximum at 0.85 μm (1.43 eV). The maximum energy conversion efficiency obtained was 18.6%. The short-circuit current, *I*_{sc} varied linearly with illumination intensity *I*_L while the open-circuit voltage *V*_{oc} was found to be proportional to (log *I*_L)². The cells were found to be stable for a period of about 10 hrs. The performance of I-/I₂ and H₂/Q/Q as redox was found to be poor.

SOLAR energy conversion using photoelectrochemical cells has been the subject of interest in recent years. Several reviews on the topic have appeared in the literature¹⁻⁶. An electrochemical solar cell is basically a photovoltaic device in which the potential barrier required for charge separation is created by the semiconductor-electrolyte junction. This type of junction has certain potential advantages over conventional solar cells employing solid-state junctions, one of the advantages being ease of junction fabrication by merely immersing the electrodes in a suitable electrolyte. In addition, the liquid-electrolyte/semiconductor contact minimizes lattice mismatch and thermal expansion problems. Besides, a wide choice and control over redox potentials in solution is also possible.

Among the favourable materials for solar energy conversion, InP with a direct band-gap of 1.35 eV at 300°K stands next only to GaAs and CdTe with a maximum theoretical efficiency⁷ of 32%. Van Wezemaal, Laflere *et al*⁸ have reported measurements of flat-band potential varying from 0.35 to 0.65 V for *n*-InP in electrolytes with pH=2-9.2. Ramprakash, Basu and Bose⁹ have recently studied the solar cell characteristics of *n*-InP and formulated the energy level diagram of *n*-InP/NaOH with [Fe(CN)₆]^{4-/3-} redox.

In the present study the spectral response of the above system, variation of open-circuit voltage *V*_{oc} and short-circuit current density *J*_{sc} with illumination intensity *I*_L, power output characteristics with different redox and stability in [Fe(CN)₆]^{4-/3-} are reported.

Experimental

A perspex cell having dimensions (4×4×6 cm³) has been constructed with provision for illumination

by a 200 watt tungsten lamp through a water filter providing an intensity upto 66 mW/cm². The intensity was varied by using different size wire meshes to act as neutral density filters. In all experiments, the intensity was measured with a calibrated 'Suryamapi' (CEL, India) solar intensity meter. During the experiment high purity Argon was bubbled through the electrolyte. All reagents were prepared from Analar grade chemicals.

The spectral response was studied using a Spectromom Spectrophotometer. The power output characteristics were studied using a Philips DC-Microvoltmeter, *V*_{oc} being measured across a 100-megohm resistance and *J*_{sc} by the voltage drop across a 1.1 ohm Manganin coil.

Small single crystal of *n*-type InP (electron concentration, *n*=2.10¹⁷ cm⁻³) obtained from M.C.P., U.K. were cut into small specimens (area=0.04 cm²) and were contacted with Indium alloyed at 400° in flowing Argon. The specimens were then lapped down to a thickness of 170 μm and washed in deionized water. The active surface i.e., the surface exposed to the electrolyte was etched for 15 seconds in (1:1) HCl:HNO₃ producing a shiny surface and was rinsed with deionized water. The specimen was then mounted in a teflon holder and the ohmic contact region was protected with Silicone rubber (Dow Corning, U. S. A.). A platinum counter electrode served as the cathode in all the experiments. The dark I-V characteristics of *n*-InP in 1M NaOH without a redox system indicated that the junction was forward-biased when InP was negative as expected.

Results and Discussion

Spectral Response :

The spectral response (Fig. 1) uncorrected for

Fig. 1. Spectral response of n-InP in 0.1M NaOH.

tungsten source intensity variation, showed a flat response with a maximum at 0.85 μm (1.43 eV) slightly higher than the bandgap of n-InP (1.35 eV) as expected. The optical absorption coefficient of InP at 0.85 μm wavelength is $2 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which results in an absorption depth of 0.5 μm . This may be compared with an absorption depth of 1.0 μm found previously for GaAs-electrolyte solar cells¹⁰ indicating superior surface properties of InP.

Dependence of V_{oc} and J_{sc} on light intensity :

The short-circuit current density J_{sc} is predicted to vary linearly with light intensity as found experimentally (Fig. 2). This is because the number of electron-hole pairs created is directly proportional to the intensity and hence as long as the collection efficiency is constant, J_{sc} will increase linearly with intensity. However at high intensities greater than

Fig. 2. Dependence of short-circuit current density J_{sc} on illumination intensity I_L for n-InP in 1M NaOH/[Fe(CN)₆]^{4-/3-} redox.

10 mW/cm^2 , for CdS, J_{sc} has been found to saturate¹¹.

The variation of open circuit photovoltage V_{oc} with intensity for solid solar cells has been usually explained according to equation

$$V_{oc} = \text{constant} + (kT/q) \ln I_L \quad \dots (1)$$

where I_L = Illumination intensity in mW/cm^2 .

However in most cases where such a variation has been observed the slope has been found to be A (kT/q) where $A=3-5$. Recently Reiss¹² has derived a very general theory specifically for semiconductor-electrolyte systems taking into account non-equilibrium space-charge effects in which, for a wide-bandgap semiconductor, it is found that

$$V_{oc} = \text{constant} + \frac{2\pi q \cdot N_D}{\epsilon_s} (\ln KI_L)^2 \quad \dots (2)$$

where K depends on material constants, N_D = donor density in cm^{-3} and ϵ_s = dielectric constant of the semiconductor.

The present results on variation of V_{oc} with I_L (Fig. 3) provide, to our knowledge, the first experimental verification of a variation such as $V_{oc} \propto (\log I_L)^2$ over an intensity range 0.4-10 mW/cm^2 .

Fig. 3. Variation of V_{oc} with $(\log I_L)^2$ where I_L is the illumination intensity in mW/cm^2 , for n-InP in 1M NaOH/[Fe(CN)₆]^{4-/3-} redox.

At high intensities a departure from such a dependence is however observed which may be due to complete filling of surface states by the high concentration of holes. In such a case transfer of

TABLE 1

$K_4[Fe(ON)_6]$ Conc.	$K_3[Fe(ON)_6]$ Conc.	V_{oc} (Volts)	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	F.F. = fill-factor = $\frac{V_{mp} \cdot J_{mp}}{V_{oc} \cdot J_{sc}}$	Solar conversion Efficiency (%)
Outer Curve 1.0M	0.5M	0.84	15.95	0.68	18.60
Inner Curve 0.5M	1.0M	0.78	19.90	0.71	15.74

* V_{mp} = Photovoltage at maximum power point ;
 ** J_{mp} = Current density at maximum power point.

holes into the electrolyte through surface states is inhibited and only direct transfer can occur, obviously at a lower rate, thus resulting in increased V_{oc} .

Power-Output Characteristics :

Fig. 4 shows two power output characteristics obtained for the system *n*-InP/1M NaOH/Pt with different redox $[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}/^{3-}$ ratios under 48.9 mW/cm² tungsten illumination. The results are summarized in Table 1.

Fig. 4. Power output characteristics for *n*-InP in 1M NaOH
 Outer Curve—1M $[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}/0.5M [Fe(CN)_6]^{3-}$
 Inner Curve—0.5M $[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}/1.0M [Fe(CN)_6]^{3-}$

Studies with I^-/I_2 and H_2Q/Q redox systems :

Some studies of the solar-cell output characteristics (Fig. 5) were made with the I^-/I_2 (Iodide/Iodine)

Fig. 5. Curve a—Power-Output characteristics for *n*-InP in 3M NaOH with 0.5M I^-/I_2 redox, under 66 mW/cm² tungsten illumination.

Curve b—Power-Output characteristics for *n*-InP in 3M NaOH with 0.5M H_2Q/Q redox, under 66 mW/cm² tungsten illumination.

and H_2Q/Q (Hydroquinone/Quinone) redox systems in 3M NaOH and the cells were stable for a period of 5 hours. The results are summarized in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Redox Conc.	V_{oc} (volts)	* I_{sc} (mA)	Fill-factor	Solar conversion efficiency (%)
Curve a 0.5M(I^-/I_2)	0.60	0.48	0.3768	0.1644
Curve b 0.5M(H_2Q/Q)	0.67	0.51	0.1485	0.0757

* I_{sc} = short-circuit current in milliamperes.

The results for the above two redox systems differ appreciably. V_{oc} and I_{sc} values are slightly greater in case of H_2Q/Q system than that obtained with I^-/I_2 system, but with the H_2Q/Q system a grey precipitate was observed on the electrode surface. This might have resulted in a decrease in the fill-factor due to an increase in series resistance.

Stability :

n-type semiconductors used in photoelectrochemical solar cells are susceptible to anodic dissolution as was found experimentally for an InP

specimen dipped in 1M NaOH without a redox. The photocurrent in this case was however small and the stability was affected due to the formation of a white precipitate of $\text{In}(\text{OH})_3$ observed on the photoanode. The decay of photocurrent with time is shown in Fig. 6(a).

Fig. 6 (a). Stability of $n\text{-InP}$ in 1M NaOH.

The addition of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-/3-}$ redox resulted in an increase of photocurrent and also the stability, due to favourable charge transfer¹¹ between the semiconductor under illumination and redox electrolyte. The photocurrent obtained was stable for a total period of 10 hrs as is shown in Fig. 6(b). A white precipitate of $\text{In}(\text{OH})_3$ covering the photoanode was observed also in this case.

Fig. 6(b). Stability of $n\text{-InP}$ in 1M NaOH, with $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-/3-}$ redox.

Conclusions :

The experiments demonstrated : (i) a spectral response maximum at 1.43 eV for InP with an absorption depth of 0.5 μm , (ii) variation of V_{oc} proportional to $[\ln I_L]^2$ and linear dependence of J_{sc} with I_L , (iii) solar conversion efficiencies of upto 18.6 % with $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-/3-}$ redox in 1M NaOH, (iv) poor conversion efficiencies with I^-/I_2 and $\text{H}_2\text{Q}/\text{Q}$ redox systems and (v) stability for 10 hrs with $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-/3-}$ redox.

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